

QUIZ**LAST NAME: SHIBUYA****FIRST NAME: YUKIHIRO****PROGRAM CODE: MMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: Word for Office 365 MSO

QUIZ: A SUMMARY OF ASSESSMENT

1. Which of the followings best describe the nature of the academic essay?

- An academic essay needs to be unique and different from any other prior research works.
- An academic essay does not require evidence if the logic is robust and precise.
- An academic essay should include relevant examples, supporting evidence and information from academic texts or credible sources¹**
- An academic essay must contain references, but if the information were obtained from the internet or interviews, they do not need to be part of the references

2. Which of the followings is an incorrect statement about plagiarism?

¹ EUCLID, *ACA-401 Coursepack. Period 1* (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 1.

- Plagiarism is a serious academic offense that can have serious consequences.
- Plagiarism is to use a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information.
- Plagiarism could occur only when authors write important academic reports such as a dissertation, master thesis, and journal papers²**
- Plagiarism can be avoided by properly citing the author or source that has provided the information you are using.

3. Which of the followings is a correct statement about the style guide?

- A style guide is a means of formatting your document so that it can fit into the grammatical requirements of your university or a journal paper that you are submitting your article to
- A style guide is mainly used in academia.
- EUCLID only accepts the reports or theses which follow the Chicago Rules (Turabian)
- A style is much more than just the correct usage of punctuation, grammar, and vocabulary³**

² EUCLID, 24-25.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Eighth edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 15.

4. Which of the followings best describe how researchers think about the research and its aims?

- Most researchers believe any research questions which could provide new knowledge and facts about the particular topic are worth exploring
- Most researchers think the research questions are valid if readers ask them, 'so what.'
- Most researchers look for specific data that they can use as evidence to test and support an answer to a question that their topic inspired them to ask⁴**
- Most researchers think intuition and spiritual insights could be valid evidence if they can be well articulated in writing.

5. Which of the followings best describe the role of the working hypothesis and its answers?

- Researchers should carefully find a question as it should be original and never be asked in any other prior researches.
- Researchers should conduct intensive document reviews of prior research before coming up with a hypothesis and its answers so that their study stay relevant in their areas of study.
- Once a working hypothesis is decided, researchers should not change it until it turns out to be irrelevant.
- Even the most tentative working hypothesis helps us think ahead, especially about the kind of evidence you'll need to support it⁵**

6. Which of the following advice is the best for the new researchers when they encounter opposing views with theirs.

⁴ Kate L. Turabian, 15.

⁵ Kate L. Turabian, 21.

- It is strongly recommended to think about other hypothesis and its answers as others will not accept your views.
- By acknowledging competing views, you show readers that you not only know those views but can respond to them confidently.⁶**
- You do not need to do anything and should focus on your research.
- It is suggested to provide a robust counter-argument to defend your views as much as possible.

7. Which of the followings is the best advice so that your report can be perceived consistent.

- Start each chapter and section by explaining your key concepts to remind the readers of your essential messages.
- Use specific terms that repeatedly refer to your concepts, not every time you mention one but often enough that readers can't miss them.⁷**
- Clearly state your key concepts and essential messages at the beginning of your report and the conclusion.
- Properly cite prior research so that you can show that your messages are consistent with other studies.

8. Which of the followings best describe the advice to the new researchers when they find no statistically significant result in their research?

⁶ Kate L. Turabian, 25

⁷ Kate L. Turabian, 45

- Researchers should immediately reject the research question and hypothesis as the obtained data is found statistically insignificant.
- Researchers should re-design their research methodology and should not employ a method that requires statistics.
- Researchers must not reject a study even if they find no statistically significant result as it is only a part of the research, and they can argue using other data for their conclusion.
- Researchers must not reject a study as inconclusive because no statistically significant differences were found as you can conclude something from even the most poorly designed experiments.⁸**

9. Which of the followings is the best advice to the researchers who plan to submit their papers to academic journals?

- Integrates, synthesizes, and critiques the research and thinking around a particular topic
- Consider the research that supports and opposes their opinions and ideas.
- Makes reasoned judgment regarding the value of other research and how it relates to their research question
- Integrates, synthesizes, and critiques the research and thinking around a particular topic
- Only essential information should be included in journal papers, and any unconfirmed information should be omitted from the documents so that the documents can stay focused, objective, and logical.⁹**

10. Which of the followings best describe the English Style Guide of the European Commission?

⁸ EUCLID, *ACA-401 Coursepack. Period 4* (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 11.

⁹ EUCLID, 6.

- The English style guide does not pay much attention to the differences in the languages used in member countries because they share similar origins and have only minor variations in grammar and spelling.
- The guide has a list of proper nouns of mountains, rivers, and lakes to standardize the English names of geographical features.
- The Commission has to deal with complex matters in English with those who do not necessarily share cultural backgrounds; therefore, they need a clear guide that provides standardized English usage to ensure access to the Commission.¹⁰**
- The guide does not recommend addressing Kings, Queens, the Pope, and Archbishop, as each country has a different cultural background.

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¹⁰ European Commission. *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission* (Brussels: Publication Office of the European Union, 2011), 1.